

THINKING THROUGH MEDIA THEORIES: UNDERSTANDING AND FURTHERING TRAUMA STUDIES¹

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ABSTRACT

Trauma studies, a field of cultural enquiry that boomed in a brief span of around a decade at the turn of 21st century, according to Marder, “has something of a privileged and paradoxical relationship to interdisciplinary studies” (2006, p. 1). One of the areas with which trauma maintains such frontier, which however has yet not drawn serious attention, is communication studies. To examine the nature of interdisciplinary connection, the paper: 1) revisits selected trauma theories setting them against major postulations in media and explores the nature of communication circuit assumed by some of the canonical trauma theories, and 2) spotlights on the applicability of the latter in understanding and opening up potential further theorization in the former. The paper begins with a brief outline of some major theoretical positions in trauma as well as in media based on the principle of reciprocal relevance. Then, it brings to light the insight of media that runs prominently but in distorted version in trauma theories to reveal how media theories paradoxically underlie in the postulations of literary trauma. Finally, it purposes possibility of interdisciplinary borrowing *i.e.*, using George Gerbner’s communication model to apprehend issues in trauma studies in general and trauma narration in particular.

KEY WORDS: trauma, media, interdisciplinary insight, Gerbner’s model

Trauma studies: Major developments and frontier

I begin with the etymology of the word though it sounds more like a cliché: trauma comes from the ancient Greek τραῦμα meaning a wound, physical scar. In sequel, *i.e.*, the development of trauma as a field of beyond bodily injury, we find it dating back to around two centuries: it first reinvigorated in medical science and then proliferated into psychoanalysis, literature and cultural studies. Among others, two explanations -- one pertaining to historical unfolding and the other related to literary crisis -- answer why trauma occupies such eminence. First line of argument reasons that the duration from mid-nineteenth to twentieth century as a witness to a series of catastrophic and cataclysmic activities ranging from railway disaster to Holocaust to Vietnam War created a congenial environment for trauma studies. Second expostulates that the prominence of trauma is a function of refuge for poststructuralists and deconstructionists when cultural critics’ attack against them heralded crisis in their preoccupation in the eighties (Radstone, 2007). The two versions, despite the point of departures in their perspectives, do not debate over the fact that trauma studies occupy a significant space in scholarly debates.

Antonio Traverso and Mick Broderick have succinctly summarized the contour of trauma studies from inception to present proliferation. In their observation, five major developments are visible:

concepts of trauma developed in psychoanalysis and, more broadly, psychology; application of post-structuralist and deconstructive concepts and methods to psychoanalytic and neurological models of trauma; philosophical reflections on historical trauma; psychoanalytic and philosophical concepts of trauma reworked through the discipline of history; and the application of a sociological framework to the understanding of cultural trauma, as a distinct category from psychological trauma. (2010, p. 8)

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Traverso and Broderick's précis covers almost all the major developments in trauma studies. For example, the first category inculcates the contribution of Jean-Martin Charcot, Sigmund Freud, Josef Breuer, Pierre Janet, Sándor Ferenczi, van der Kolk and van der Hart, and many other psychoanalysts and psychiatrists². The second development encompasses the work of Cathy Caruth, Shoshana Felman, Dori Laub and Geoffrey Hartman³. The works of Christine van Boheemen-Saaf (1999), Allen Meek (2010), among others can be put under the third group. The fourth classification includes mostly the works of Dominick LaCapra (1994, 1998, 2001). And, the last category circumscribes the works of scholars such as Kai Erikson, Ron Eyerman, Jeffrey Alexander⁴. Clearly, the scholarship in trauma has been immensely diverse and addressed various interdisciplinary concerns such as trauma and historiography, trauma and trans-Atlantic slave trade, trauma and colonialism and so on.

Nonetheless, the development so far has not amply broached the nexus between trauma and communication even after a serious and thought provoking call from one of the precursors of the field, Cathy Caruth. In her seminal book, *Trauma: Explorations in Memory*, which is believed to have ushered trauma in literature from medical sciences, Caruth has contended that the issues in trauma "unsettles and forces us to rethink our notion of experience and of communication" (1995, p. 4). The postulation in a typical post-modern voice leaves us with the sense that trauma ruptures entire corpus of received epistemology on communication. If, as Caruth argued, traumatic events compel to retrospect our understanding of communication, then, scholars in media and communication studies must answer the questions such as a) does trauma really defy received notions of communication, and if it does so, i) what role do the interlocutors in canonical notion of communication perform, ii) what is the nature of message and feedback in the process, iii) how does the channel function, and iv) what nature of communication circuit does trauma generate. Following Caruth's concern, the paper sets out to examine major takes in trauma in the light of media theories as an attempt to answer some of the above mentioned concerns. I find it appropriate to start with the discussion on some of the fundamentals in media theories before the paper shifts focus to the interrelationship of media and trauma.

Media theories: Perspectives and postulations

Media theories, in general, postulate on social, political, economic and psychological dynamics of media and society. In other words, media theories elucidate how advancement in technology/ audience-ship of media correlates with societal functions or vice versa.

A cursory glance at the knot of media and society reveals that since 16th century the interdisciplinary insight has been one of the most productive sites of media theory formulation. Grounding on the nexus of newspaper and society, or radio and society, or any new media and society, the theories have hypothesized on different aspects. An underlying assumption in almost all the theories is that media operate significantly in many domains of society including politics and culture. As McQuail observes, the relation between media and society has both a political dimension and a normative or social-cultural aspects (2001). He presents two-fold function of media in politics to explicate the connection: one, as "an essential element in the process of democratic politics"; and two, as "a means of exercising power". Similarly, in relation to culture, media function as "primary source of definitions and images of social reality and the most ubiquitous expression of shared identity" (p. 4). The multi-functional dimension of media clearly shows how ubiquitous it has been.

The ubiquity of media both as producer and disseminator of meanings has ignited debates on its pragmatics and resulted in numerous theories. McQuail has categorized the debating perspectives under four major headings: media-culturalist, media-materialist, social-culturalist and social materialist. These perspectives, he suggests, produce four kinds of theory – social scientific, normative, operational and everyday (p. 7). In comparison to McQuail's spectrum, the formulation of Baron and Davis differs in many respects. According to them, media theories can be categorized into four types: mass media theory, limited effects perspective, cultural perspectives and meaning making perspective (2010, pp. 11-38). The paper sheds light on only the pertinent ones to set against some trauma theories as the discussion over all the types is beyond the scope of the project.

² See Micale and Lerner (2001) for a detail analysis of scholarly discussion in this period; Wastel (2005) and Kaplan (2005) for an analysis of Freud's contribution.

³ Deriving ideas from medical sciences, especially from the definition of Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), the scholars extended the notion both in analyzing literary representation of trauma and reconstruction of traumatic history. See Felman and Laub (1992); Caruth (1995, 1996); Hartman (1995).

⁴ See Alexander et. al. (2004); Eyerman (2001)

Trauma in/of media

Media has been one of the most desired projection sites of traumatic events. Whether it was during Iraq war, or 9/11 in America, or 7/11 in India, media constantly catered the scenes of trauma. Traverso and Broderick's observation on the portrayal of catastrophe, atrocity, suffering and death in media, sounds very succinct: "During the past 100 years or so, traumatic historical events and experiences have been re-imagined and re-enacted for us to witness over and over by constantly evolving media and art form" (2010, p. 3). Indeed, media has been global carriers of traumatic events. Despite such correlation, there has been only scanty attention to explore the association of media and trauma. Among limited studies, Baran and Davis, for example, have analyzed how Hitler used new media of his time during Holocaust. "German Nazis," they write, "improved on World War I propaganda techniques and ruthlessly exploited new media technology like motion pictures and radio to consolidate their power" (2010, p. 29). Clearly, the assessment reiterates one of the most frequent views that typify understanding of scholars during mass society theory⁵, an era when media was used by dictators for exercising power.

Media in trauma studies

Leaving apart such a few scholarships from media scholars, the analysis of Nazis' use of media in particular and other people's use in general by trauma scholars has almost been negligible. Even when the connection is explored, scholars have attempted to sanctify the nexus and thereby negate the possibility of producing critical appreciation⁶.

With the above argument, I do not intend to imply absence of quality scholarship in trauma studies; I mean to say that it is very insular and the nature of interrelationship has not been explored aptly. In isolation, the fields such as medical sciences, psychology, literature, cultural inquiry, among others, have raised concern on multiple aspects of individuals and society that emerge from trauma. Consequently, many issues including the effect of trauma on memory (Freud and Breuer, 1895; Appelbaum, Uyehara, Elen ed., 1997), need to vicariously witness (Felman and Laub, 1992), alternative historiography (LaCapra, 1998), nature of testimony (Caruth, 1996), cultural cohesion (Alexander, 2004; Eyerman, 2001), and extension of trauma to non-western cases (Scraps and Buelens, 2008) have been comprehensively brought. Yet, trauma in relation to media, as I mean to state, has appeared very sparsely and sporadically.

An early instance of trauma in relation to media can be traced in the writings of Judith Herman (1992). Herman broadly brings the issue of power in Louis Althusser's sense of state apparatus and shows how study into trauma has suffered from intermittent amnesia. The insight, however, does not shed light enough to address nuances of media issues. Apart from Herman's concern, it is curious to see many trauma scholars showing either apologetic or amnesiac interest to media though the very foundation of the theory is Holocaust. Moreover, we hardly find them examining the propagandist value of media exploited by Hitler. For instance, Felman defends Paul de Man, one who had supported Nazi cause during the War as correspondent, apologetically instead of investigating the nuances of the issue stating: "de Man's silence has an altogether different personal and historical significance, and thus has much profound and far-reaching implication than this simplistic psychological interpretation can either suspect or account for" (1992, p. 121). Similarly, Caruth demonstrates amnesiac attitude. A close content-analysis of her work reveals hardly any noticeable extension of her call to examine how trauma forces us to rethink our notion of communication. The reason for such a disregard even after raising the issue can widely be guessed to be located in her fundamental understanding of trauma: "..., trauma is described as the response to an unexpected or overwhelming violent event or events that are not fully grasped as they occur, but return later in repeated flashbacks, nightmares, and other repetitive phenomena" (1996, p. 91). In her observations, the schema of traumatic event in relation to the traumatized appears so encompassing that the victim seems to find no refuge to two-way symmetrical communication process⁷. I will discuss this issue under subheadings below.

⁵ Among the four eras outlined by Baran and Davis, mass media theory covers the span from around the mid of 19th to first four decades of 20th century. They view media as a powerful weapon "to profoundly shape our perceptions of the social world and to manipulate our actions, often without our conscious awareness"; and thereby argue that "media influence must be controlled" (p. 46).

⁶ See the discussion below on Laub and Felman, and Caruth.

⁷ Grunnig and Hunt (1984). Unlike the other three forms of communication – two-way asymmetrical, public information and press agency model – two-way symmetrical model emphasizes on dialogue and thereby the potential of active interaction.

A major break in the silence about media in trauma can be tracked to September 11 attack in twin-tower. In Ann Kaplan's words, "The phenomenon of 9/11 was perhaps the supreme example of a catastrophe that was experienced globally via digital technologies (Internet, cell phones) as well as by television and radio". Based on this observation, Kaplan argues for the examination of mediated trauma because "most people encounter trauma through the media" (2005, p. 2). Kaplan's reinforcement to Herman's ostensive acknowledgement of media is certainly a call for investigating the process of trauma with no further bracketing of media. The invitation in 2005, it can be seen, has catered an important orientation: we can find some noticeable responses thereafter.

The number of publications demonstrates increased magnitude of the concern⁸ when we examine the availability of the books that combine media and trauma. One of such area where we can find such interest is cultural trauma: a theory which assumes that certain events such as Trans-Atlantic slave trade inherently traumatize a large collective even now. In addition, there is a field, screen studies, which primarily concerns visual representation and trauma. This paper, however, does not discuss this domain as the focus is on earlier theories. In the section below, I examine the nature of treatment given to the components of communication in some of the above mentioned theories and a few other canonical theories of trauma.

Felman, Laub and media

The two pioneer scholars in trauma studies, psychoanalyst Dori Laub and Yale literary critic Shoshana Felman endeavour "to grasp and to articulate the obscure relation between witnessing, events and evidence" (1992). In their collaborative work *Testimony: Crises of Witnessing in Literature, Psychoanalysis, and History*, they argue for the urgency to vicariously traumatize as Holocaust is "an event without a witness" (pp. xiii-xvii). Felman finds it necessary to examine the relationship between pedagogy and trauma. Based on her experiment in the seminar class of Yale graduate students, she concludes, "a 'life testimony' is not simply a testimony to a private life, but a point of conflation between text and life, a textual testimony which can *penetrate us like an actual life*". In other words, she aims to construct testimony, "composed of bits and pieces of memory that has been overwhelmed by occurrences that have not settled into understanding or remembrance" (p. 2, 5). Similarly, Laub contributes to this necessity by primarily investigating the impact of listening to traumatic experience. The experience, he contends, "precludes its registration; the observing and recording mechanisms of the human mind are temporarily knocked out, malfunction". Yet, the hearer becomes "the blank screen on which the event comes to be inscribed for the first time" (p. 57). In both the postulations, we find the authors invoking essential components of communication with due significance to encoding and decoding of traumatic event.

Since they emphasize on meaning making and thereby transmitting trauma, I find bringing Schramm's model⁹ (figure 1) appropriate to elucidate their notion. The model, as explained by Schramm, assumes a source which encodes message and transmits it to the intended destination. Then, the message is decoded based on the receiver's overlapped field of experience with the speaker.

⁸ See, for instance, Zelier and Allan, ed. (2002); Feinstein (2001); Cramer and Owen (2003); Moorcraft and Taylor (2008); and Meek (2010).

⁹ Emphasizing the process of encoding and decoding in sender as well as receiver, Schramm (1961) points out that source and the destination must have same field of experience for understanding to take place.

Figure 1: Wilbur Schramm's model (Source: Croft, 2004)

The first thing to note in Felman and Laub is the erasure of an individual who in Schramm's model encodes based on the function of sensory mechanism. The process of encoding does not occur because the person's normal cognition mechanism becomes defunct at the site of trauma. In addition, language as a medium fails to convey traumatic experience. So, the primary encoder in Schramm's diagram plays hardly any role. In their schema, to bring Craps and Buelens (2008) insight:

The respective subject positions into which the witness and the listener/reader are interpellated are those of a passive, inarticulate victim on the one hand and a knowledgeable expert on the other. The former bears witness to a truth of which he or she is not fully conscious, and can do so only indirectly, making it impossible for his or her testimony to act as a political intervention. The latter responds to the witness's testimony by showing empathy, a reaction that supposedly obviates any need for critical self-reflection regarding his or her own implication in ongoing practices of oppression and denial, let alone political mobilization against those practices. (pp. 4-5)

Even in the absence of encoder's agency, the message avails to the receiver in the form of testimonial account, which is the only form of possible message. When the testimony reaches the hearer or reader, decoding process starts so as to endow meaning to the traumatic event. The next element in communication – feedback which is thought to be essential to make encoding-decoding more friendly – disappears from the circuit. What appears then is a reminder of Roland Barth's notion of author's birth at the hands of reader progenitor (1977, pp. 142-148).

Caruth and Media

Cathy Caruth's take on trauma mainly centers on the nature of belatedness *i.e.*, the period from traumatic event to its later manifestation. Referring to Freud's surprise at the literal return of the event in traumatized individuals, she emphasizes on the importance of "understand [ing] the nature of suffering, without eliminating the force and truth of the reality that trauma survivors face and quite often try to transmit it to us" (1995, p. vii). The ethical imperative implied through the notion of belatedness demands a peculiar role from the witness. So, the hermeneutical enterprise to be undertaken appears highly paradoxical. How enigmatic the idea sounds can be discerned from Caruth's claim expressed in the following lines: "trauma opens up and challenges us to a new kind of listening, the witnessing, precisely, of *impossibility*" (p. 10).

If, as Caruth argues, trauma calls for a new kind of listening, then what special form of communication circuit she envisions becomes a pertinent question. As a scholar approaching trauma from communication domain, I respond to the question setting it in a broader frame of existing communication model. More specifically, I examine Caruth's idea setting it against Aristotle's model to which Stone, Singletary and Richmond have called "the primary source of communication theories for people living in democratic societies" (2003, p. 2). The model comprises three elements – speaker, message and listener – bounded by the speaker's intention to impart desired effect. The linear model envisioned in Aristotle's notion of rhetoric appears as shown in Fig 2:

Figure 2: Aristotle's model of communication (Source: Croft, 2004)

In Caruth's postulation, none of the components as outlined in figure 2 appear functioning the way they are envisioned by Aristotle. Instead, Aristotle's speaker in Caruth becomes dysfunctional due to the fact that "the most direct seeing of a violent event may occur as an absolute inability to know it" (1995, p. 218). The defunct nature of traumatized subject's consciousness allows no direct agency to message. Further in the process, the listener also does not accomplice the speaker to attain desired effect if s/he has any. Consequently, the fundamental situation of communication becomes mumbo jumbo. In Caruth's words, "This speaking and this listening – a speaking and a listening *from the site of trauma* – does not rely, I would suggest, on what we simply know of each other, but on what we don't know of our own traumatic past" (p. 11). The dysfunction in the whole mechanism is due to the failure of speaker whose function in Aristotle's model comprise of invention, arrangement, style, memory and delivery. Unlike Aristotle's speaker, the traumatized subject in Caruth cannot be conscious of essentials in effective communication namely, logos, pathos and ethos. Moreover, the castration of speaker's arrangement and style as a consequence of traumatic experience provides no scope for memory and thus the speaker fails to deliver. In sum, Caruth's schema of trauma when set against Aristotelian frame of communication, I argue, elucidates archetypal postmodernist position over the linear model of communication.

Cultural trauma and media

Cultural trauma refers to the traumatization of a larger unit of individuals sharing the same culture due to atrocious event in the community. Because trauma causes "tear in the social fabric," it develops a phenomenon of collective identity (Eyerman, 2001, p. 2). In Alexander's words, cultural trauma refers to a situation "when members of a collective feel they have been subjected to a horrendous event that leaves indelible marks upon their group consciousness, marking their memories for ever, and changing their future identity in fundamental and irrevocable ways" (2004, p. 1). The nature of impact upon the group, as cultural trauma theorists like Eyerman argue, depends on multiple factors; one of them is the role of public reflection and discourse: "Here, mass-mediated representations play a decisive role. This is also the case in what we have called cultural trauma". Elucidating further, he writes:

[traumatic] experience is usually mediated through newspaper, radio, or television, Mass mediated experience always involves selective construction and representation since what is seen is the result of the actions and decisions of professionals as to what is significant and how it should be presented. (2001, pp. 2-3)

The idea of "selective construction and representation" at the core of cultural trauma theory reiterates two widely known theories of communication – two step flow and agenda-setting theory. The essence of two-step¹⁰ lies at the role acknowledged for opinion leaders. As powerful intermediaries, the leaders have ability to frame the message and use them as per their interest. Another insight which can be useful to understand cultural trauma is agenda-setting theory formulated by McCombs and Shaw (1972) based on their investigation of presidential campaigns in the seventies. The theory concerns how the agenda of media becomes a public agenda.

¹⁰ See Lazarsfeld, Berelson, Gaudet (1944); Katz and Lazarsfeld (1955)

Noelle-Neumann (1973), and Gerbner and Gross (1974) have also argued along the line of McCombs and Shaw's formulation. When the two-step flow and agenda-setting are put together in the context of Trans-Atlantic slave trade, we can understand what cultural trauma theory intends to do. It becomes clear that trauma experience to become a source of cultural identity needs the role of opinion leaders initially and the responsibility of media later.

Beginning

The examination of scholarship in trauma through media theories, as done above, demonstrates how the latter can facilitate understanding of the former or vice versa. With this picture in mind, I find another question worthy to put. Can we consider borrowing any other more comprehensive model of communication for an alternative in trauma theorization? For instance, the model developed by George Gerbner? The potential, I propose, is significantly high because of the broad spectrum visible in the model as shown in figure 3.

The model brings ten elements in communication process namely person, event, reaction, situation, means, availability, form, context, conveying context and consequences. As shown in the model, communication begins with M (someone), a communicating agent, a perceiver and a reactor. The process of perception and reaction is constrained by the factors like situation and means consecutively. In the next step when the message is communicated, it aims to transfer the perceived message. Finally, when it reaches the listener, it is perceived in certain context and as a consequence brings some result.

Figure 3: Basic generalized graphic model [Source: Gerbner, 1956, p. 175]

Because the model incorporates elements from perception to rendition, its applicability in other than strictly communication has already drawn attention of scholars in many fields. To use an assessment of a prominent scholar in media, the model's applicability is its wider function: "it can explain any example of communication [,] and in particular draws attention to those key elements that are common to each and every act of communication" (Fiske, 2002, p. 24).

Based on the two observations a) strength of the model due to its incorporation of major elements of communication from perception to cognition and ultimately to affective processing when set in the context of postulations in trauma, and b) continuous call for alternative to canonical trauma theories, the paper hypothesizes that Gerbner's model can be a stepping stone in formulating an alternative framework. I conclude with an optimistic note and an invitation to the scholars in trauma as well as in media studies for collaborative exploration of this possibility.

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